

Teachers' Affective Factors and Retention Rates in Private School

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Abstract. This study investigated the teachers' affective factors and retention rates in a private school. It specifically identified the level of affective factors of teachers in private schools, the level of retention rates, and the significant differences in the level of teachers' affective factors when grouped according to length of service and position. The study sought to provide a better understanding of how affective factors contribute to teacher retention and organizational stability in a private educational institution. Using a descriptive-quantitative research design, data were collected from 97 teachers at Claret School of Zamboanga City through a researcher-developed instrument. The findings revealed that teachers in Claret School of Zamboanga City are very highly satisfied with their jobs, very highly attached to the institution, and possess a very high level of loyalty and commitment to the school. These results indicate that teachers generally maintain positive perceptions and strong emotional connections with their workplace. Among the variables examined, the results showed that length of service has no significant difference in the level of affective factors, whereas position in the workplace has a significant difference. This suggests that teachers' roles and responsibilities may influence their level of satisfaction, attachment, loyalty, and commitment within the institution. This study highlights the need to continue strengthening workplace conditions, professional development opportunities, and institutional support systems. Since job satisfaction, emotional attachment, and commitment are already high, sustaining these factors can help improve teacher retention and reduce turnover rates in private schools. Future studies should explore other factors affecting teacher retention, such as salary, workload balance, leadership style, school culture, and other organizational influences that may affect teachers' decisions to remain in their profession.

Keywords: Affective Factors; Job Commitment; Job Satisfaction; Private School; Retention Rates

Introduction

Education plays an important role in the development of individuals and the community. Teachers, as the principal medium of learning, greatly influence students' academic achievement and holistic growth. However, many teachers resign from private schools due to lower salaries and limited benefits, even if they do not want to leave. Most private school teachers transfer to public schools to gain better salaries, benefits, and financial stability for their families (Philstar Global, 2023). This situation has become a growing concern for private schools in retaining trained and experienced teachers.

Despite this reality, some teachers decide to remain in private schools even though they know that public schools offer bigger salaries and benefits. According to Anog (2024), job satisfaction, commitment, and loyalty strongly influence teachers' decisions to stay. These are considered Affective Factors, which refer to emotional states, feelings, attitudes, and internal dispositions that influence a person's behavior and decisions (NueroLaunch, 2025). Studies also show that teachers who feel valued, emotionally supported, and satisfied are more likely to remain in their profession, while stress, burnout, and dissatisfaction may lead to resignation (Rotas and Cahapay, 2021).

Despite existing studies on teacher retention, there is limited research that focuses on the relationship between affective factors and retention in private schools. Therefore, this study aims to determine the level of Affective Factors in terms of job satisfaction, emotional attachment, and loyalty, and identify whether significant differences exist when grouped according to length of service and position. By identifying the affective factors influencing teachers' decisions, the findings may help school administrators develop strategies to improve teacher satisfaction, reduce turnover, commitment among teachers, and enhance the quality of education and stability of private schools.

Research Questions

This research aims to answer the following questions:

1. What are the levels of teachers' affective factors in the private school in terms of;
 - 1.1 job satisfaction;
 - 1.2 emotional attachment; and
 - 1.3 commitment/loyalty
2. What are the retention rates of teachers in private schools?
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of teachers' affective factors in the private school in terms of;
 - 3.1 length of service
 - 3.2 position

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study examines the affective factors and retention rates of private school teachers at Claret School of Zamboanga City during School Year 2025–2026. It focuses on job satisfaction, emotional attachment, and commitment or loyalty, and determines significant differences based on length of service and position. The respondents include ninety-seven licensed teachers from departments, while non-licensed and probationary teachers are excluded. Data were analyzed in SPSS software.

Literature Review

Affective Factors and Retention Rates

Affective factors refer to the emotional states, attitudes, and internal dispositions of individuals that influence their behavior, decisions, and actions within the workplace. In the context of teaching, these include job satisfaction, emotional attachment, and commitment, all of which play a crucial role in shaping teachers' retention decisions. Anog et al. (2024) explained that affective factors significantly influence teachers' willingness to stay in private schools, as positive emotional experiences strengthen retention. Ibrahim and Al-Saadi (2023) further supported that supportive work environments enhance affective responses, leading to lower turnover intention. Meanwhile, Ongaki (2017) emphasized that emotional and attitudinal factors are as important as external conditions in determining teacher retention. Overall, affective factors strongly impact retention rates by shaping how teachers feel about their work, school environment, and professional relationships. Since affective factors encompass various emotional and attitudinal dimensions that influence teachers' decisions to remain in their institutions, it is important to examine the specific components that contribute to retention. One of the most widely studied affective factors is job satisfaction, which has consistently been associated with teachers' intentions to stay in their schools.

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is considered a key determinant of teacher retention, as it directly influences teachers' willingness to remain in their current institutions. Ibrahim and Al-Saadi (2023) emphasized that job satisfaction, supported by strong organizational support, significantly reduces teachers' turnover intention and strengthens retention. In the Philippine context, Anog, de Vera, and Peteros (2024) found that private school teachers with higher levels of job satisfaction are more likely to stay in their institutions due to fulfillment in workload, support systems, and professional growth opportunities. Similarly, Ongaki (2017) noted that job satisfaction is a critical factor influencing teachers' decisions to remain in the teaching profession. These studies collectively suggest that when teachers feel satisfied with their working environment, they are less likely to leave, thereby improving retention rates in schools. While job satisfaction reflects teachers' overall contentment with their work and professional environment, retention is also influenced by the emotional bonds teachers develop within their institutions. Therefore, understanding emotional attachment provides a deeper perspective on how personal connections and a sense of belonging contribute to teachers' decisions to remain in their schools.

Emotional Attachment

Emotional attachment plays an important role in teachers' decision to remain in their schools, as it reflects their sense of belonging and connection to the school community. According to Anog et al. (2024), teachers who develop strong emotional ties with their colleagues, students, and institution are more likely to demonstrate loyalty and remain in their current workplace. This attachment is often strengthened through positive school culture and supportive relationships within the institution. Furthermore, the OECD (2019) highlights that supportive school environments contribute to stronger emotional engagement among

teachers, which may reduce turnover intention. Emotional attachment also influences teachers' resilience in facing workplace challenges, making them more committed to staying despite external opportunities. Thus, emotional connection within the school setting is a significant factor that enhances teacher retention. Beyond emotional attachment, teachers' decisions to remain in an institution are also shaped by their level of commitment and loyalty. Although emotional attachment focuses on feelings of connection and belonging, commitment and loyalty reflect a teacher's dedication to organizational goals and willingness to continue serving the institution over time.

Commitment/Loyalty

Commitment and loyalty are essential predictors of teacher retention, as they reflect teachers' dedication to their profession and institution. Oberes and Tan (2022) found that organizational commitment significantly reduces turnover intention among private school teachers, indicating that highly committed teachers are more likely to remain in their schools. Similarly, Anog et al. (2024) emphasized that teachers who exhibit strong loyalty and alignment with school goals tend to stay longer in their institutions despite external opportunities. Kim and Park (2022) also noted that teachers' perceptions of their roles and positions within the school influence their level of commitment and engagement. These studies suggest that when teachers feel a strong sense of responsibility and loyalty toward their institution, their likelihood of leaving decreases, thereby strengthening retention rates in private schools. Collectively, the literature suggests that job satisfaction, emotional attachment, and commitment or loyalty are important affective factors that influence teacher retention. Although previous studies have examined these variables individually and in various educational settings, limited research has explored their combined influence on retention rates among teachers in private schools in Zamboanga City. This gap in the literature provides the basis for the present study, which seeks to investigate teachers' affective factors and retention rates in a private school context.

Methodology

Research Design

This study uses a descriptive quantitative design to determine the level of teachers' affective factors in private schools and identify if there is a significant difference when grouped according to length of service and position. Descriptive-quantitative research design is a research method that uses numerical data to describe characteristics, trends, or conditions of a population without manipulating variables. It focuses on collecting measurable data and analyzing it through statistical methods (Creswell, 2014). Thus, this research design helps address the study by measuring and describing the level of teachers' affective factors and retention rates in private schools. It also allows the researcher to use appropriate statistical analysis to determine whether there is a significant difference in teachers' affective factors when grouped according to length of service.

Sampling Design

The population of the study consists of 97 licensed professional teachers of Claret School of Zamboanga City during School Year 2025–2026, including teachers from the Grade School, High School, and Senior High School departments. Licensed teachers currently assigned to office positions are also included if they previously served as classroom teachers. Non-licensed and probationary teachers are excluded from the study. This research uses convenience sampling since the respondents are readily accessible to the researcher. Convenience sampling is a non-probability sampling method where participants are selected based on accessibility. The sampling procedure includes identifying the population, applying the sampling method, and selecting qualified respondents.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at Claret School of Zamboanga City, a private Catholic institution located along Ruste Drive, San Jose Road, Zamboanga City, Philippines. It was established in 1966, and it began as an exclusive school for boys and later became a co-educational institution. The school offers preschool, grade school, junior high school, and senior high school programs. It is known for academic excellence, holistic development, and values formation grounded in Christian principles. The school was chosen because of its accessibility, availability of respondents, and relevance to the study, making it suitable for gathering data on teachers' affective factors and retention in private schools.

Research Participants

The respondents of this study are licensed professional teachers of Claret School of Zamboanga City during School Year 2025–2026. They include teachers from the Grade School, High School, and Senior High School departments, as well as licensed teachers currently assigned to administrative or office positions who previously served as classroom teachers. A total of 97 teachers participated in the study.

Research Instrument

The study aims to determine the level of teachers' affective factors in private schools in terms of job satisfaction, emotional attachment, and loyalty, as well as their retention rates. It also examines whether there is a significant difference in affective factors when grouped according to length of service and position. The researcher will use a survey questionnaire with two parts: Part I for respondents' profiles and Part II for measuring affective factors using a four-point Likert scale, where 4 – Strongly Agree, 3 – Agree, 2 – Disagree, and 1 – Strongly Disagree. Data on retention rates will be obtained from official records of Claret School of Zamboanga City through the Human Resource Office. The study will use data mining with proper permission and strict confidentiality. ANOVA will determine significant differences using SPSS.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data for this study were gathered through a series of systematic procedures. First, the researcher sought permission from the School Director of Claret School of Zamboanga City to conduct the study within the institution. After obtaining approval, a formal letter of permission was prepared and submitted to the concerned authorities. Before the distribution of the research instruments, the questionnaires underwent validation by qualified experts to ensure the accuracy and credibility of the instruments. After the validation process, pilot testing was conducted to assess and establish the reliability of the questionnaire. Following this, informed consent forms were prepared and distributed to the respondents to secure their voluntary participation in the study. The respondents were then properly oriented regarding the objectives, purpose, and procedures of the study. During the orientation, the researcher also explained the expected duration of participation and assured the respondents that their responses would be treated with confidentiality. Furthermore, the researcher informed the participants that the language used in the research instrument was English to ensure consistency and clarity in gathering the data.

Results and Discussions

Research Question 1: What are the levels of teachers' affective factors in the private school in terms of job satisfaction, emotional attachment, and commitment/loyalty?

Table 1. Level of Teachers' Affective Factors I Private School in terms of Job Satisfaction

	Statements	Mean	Verbal
1.	Expresses satisfaction with the current teaching workload.	3.32	Very High
2.	Shows contentment with the school's working conditions.	3.18	High
3.	Acknowledges satisfaction with administrative support.	3.00	High
4.	Reports satisfaction with professional growth opportunities.	3.32	Very High
5.	Conveys fulfillment with overall teaching experience in the school.	3.34	Very High
	Overall Mean	3.232	Very High

Table 1 shows the levels of teachers' affective factors in the private school in terms of job satisfaction. The findings showed that the highest mean was "Conveys fulfillment with overall teaching experience in the school" (M = 3.34, Very High), indicating that teachers feel fulfilled in their teaching roles, which may encourage them to remain in private school. The second-highest mean was shared by "Expresses satisfaction with the current teaching workload" and "Reports satisfaction with professional growth opportunities" (M = 3.32, Very High), indicating that manageable workload and professional development opportunities may strengthen teachers' willingness to stay in the aforementioned school. Meanwhile, the lowest mean was "Acknowledges satisfaction with administrative support" (M = 3.00, High), implying that improving administrative support may help increase teacher retention. The second lowest mean was "Shows contentment with the school's working conditions" (M = 3.18, High), indicating that better workplace conditions and resources may further encourage teachers to stay. Overall, the findings indicate that teachers in private schools have a Very High level of job satisfaction (M = 3.232), which implies positive experiences that may contribute to their decision to remain and continue teaching at the said school. This finding is supported by the study of Maria Domnena Inso Anog, John Virtucio de Vera, and Emerson De Luna Peteros

(2024), which found that job satisfaction is significantly related to teacher retention in a Philippine private school, suggesting that positive work experiences, administrative support, and professional growth opportunities can influence teachers' decisions to stay in their institution.

Table 2. Level of Teachers' Affective Factors I Private School in terms of Emotional Attachment

Statements	Mean	Verbal
1. Demonstrates a strong sense of belonging to the school.	3.40	Very High
2. Builds positive emotional ties within the school community.	3.34	Very High
3. Maintains emotional connection with students, colleagues, and school culture.	3.38	Very High
4. Displays pride in association with the school.	3.34	Very High
5. Shows emotional difficulty when leaving the school.	3.38	Very High
Overall Mean	3.368	Very High

Table 2 shows the levels of teachers' affective factors in the private school in terms of emotional attachment. The findings showed that the highest mean was "Maintains emotional connection with students, colleagues, and school culture, and shows emotional difficulty when leaving the school" (M=3.38, Very High), indicating that teachers are attached and connected emotionally to their students, colleagues, and school culture. In addition, this indicates that teachers at private schools find it emotionally difficult to leave the school. This implies that teachers' decision to remain in private school stems from their emotional attachment to their students, colleagues, and school culture. On the other hand, the lowest mean was shared by "Builds positive emotional ties within the school community" and "Displays pride in association with the school" (M = 3.34, Very High). This means that while teachers already have a strong emotional connection to their school, improving relationships and increasing pride in the institution may help strengthen their attachment and encourage them to stay longer. Overall, the findings indicate that teachers in private schools have a Very High level of emotional attachment (M = 3.368), which implies that emotional attachment helps teachers stay in private schools. This is supported by Oberes and Tan (2022), who found that teachers with stronger emotional attachment or commitment to their school are less likely to leave and are more likely to stay in their teaching positions.

Table 3. Level of Teachers' Affective Factors I Private School in terms of Commitment/Loyalty

Statements	Mean	Verbal
1. Commits to continued service despite challenges.	3.50	Very High
2. Exerts additional effort for the school's success.	3.40	Very High
3. Aligns professional decisions with the school's goals and values.	3.42	Very High
4. Plans to remain in the institution for an extended period.	3.04	High
5. Upholds loyalty even when alternative opportunities arise.	3.16	High
Overall Mean	3.30	Very High

Table 3 shows the levels of teachers' affective factors in the private school in terms of commitment or loyalty. The highest indicator was "Commits to continued service despite challenges" (M=3.50, Very High). This is followed by "Aligns professional decisions with the school's goals and values" (M=3.42, Very High). This implies that teachers commit themselves to giving service to the school because they align their decisions with the school's goals and values. Meanwhile, the lowest were "Plans to remain in the institution for an extended period" (M = 3.04, High) and "Upholds loyalty even when alternative opportunities arise" (M = 3.16, High). This implies that although teachers are committed, improving support, career growth, and working conditions may further strengthen their loyalty and intention to stay. This is supported by Ongaki (2017), who stated that better school support and opportunities can help increase teacher retention and reduce turnover.

Research Question 2: What are the retention rates of teachers in private schools?

Table 4. The Level of Retention Rates of Claret School of Zamboanga City for the School Year 2025-2026

Teachers	Frequency	Percentage
Retention Rates	68	70%
Turn Over Rates	29	30%

Total 97 100%

Table 4 shows that Table 4 shows the retention rates of teachers in Claret School of Zamboanga City for the school year 2025-2026. There are 97 teachers in Claret School of Zamboanga City. 68 teachers stayed while 29 resigned. The retention rates are 70%, and the turnover rates are only 30%. This implies that 70 percent of these teachers stayed in private schools because they are satisfied with their job, emotionally attached to their pupils, colleagues, and the school's culture, and committed/loyal to the school. Overall, the results show a high teacher retention rate (70%) and low turnover rate (30%), indicating that most teachers remain in the school due to positive work experiences. This implies that job satisfaction, emotional attachment, and commitment/loyalty play important roles in teachers' decisions to stay in private schools. Anog, de Vera, and Peteros (2024) found that teacher retention is significantly influenced by job satisfaction and school commitment, which are strengthened by positive working conditions.

Research Question 3: Is there a significant difference in the level of teachers' affective factors in the private school in terms of length of service, and position?

Table 5. Significant Difference in the Level of Teachers' Affective Factors in Terms of Length of Service

Independent Variable	Length of Service	Mean	T-Value	P-Value	Interpretation
Length of Service	1-3 Years	3.11	1.016	.479	No significant difference
	4-6 years	3.20			
	7-10 years	3.20			
	11 years and above	3.53			

Table 5 presents the level of responses of teachers when grouped according to length of service. The results show the level of teachers' responses in terms of length of service, with means ranging from 3.11 to 3.53. Teachers with 11 years and above obtained the highest mean ($M = 3.53$), while those with 1–3 years of service obtained the lowest mean ($M = 3.11$). However, the computed t-value of 1.016 with a p-value of .479 indicates that there is no significant difference in responses according to length of service. This implies that teachers, regardless of years in service, have similar perceptions of the variable studied. This suggests that experience does not strongly influence their responses, and that other factors such as job satisfaction and school environment may play a greater role in shaping their views. This is supported by OECD (2019), which reported that teacher perceptions and attitudes are often more influenced by school working conditions and support systems than by years of teaching experience.

Table 6. Significant Difference in the Level of Teachers' Affective Factors in Terms of Position

Independent Variable	Position	Mean	T-Value	P-Value	Interpretation
Position	Junior Teachers	3.11	-3.781	0.000	significant difference
	Administrators	3.20			

Table 6 presents the level of responses of teachers when grouped according to position. The results show a significant difference between junior teachers and Subject Area Coordinators/Head Offices/administrators ($p = 0.000$), with administrators obtaining a slightly higher mean ($M = 3.20$) compared to junior teachers ($M = 3.11$). This means that junior teachers and administrators have different views because of their different roles and responsibilities in the school. This is supported by recent studies, which show that job position influences teachers' perceptions since administrators and teachers experience different levels of authority, workload, and decision-making involvement, which affect how they view school practices and working conditions (Kim & Park, 2022).

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to strict ethical standards in the collection and handling of data. Prior to the conduct of the research, permission was secured from the school principal and the relevant authorities of Claret School of Zamboanga City. Participation in the study was voluntary, and respondents were informed of the purpose of the research before answering the questionnaire. They were also given the right to refuse participation or withdraw at any time without any negative consequences. The names of respondents were used in the data collection, and their names were de-identified. Confidentiality was observed, and all data

were handled with care and used solely for academic and research purposes. The information gathered was not shared with unauthorized individuals. Furthermore, all data were handled in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 of the Republic of the Philippines. The researcher ensured honesty, integrity, and transparency throughout the research process to avoid bias or misrepresentation of results.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, teachers in private schools generally experience a very high level of job satisfaction, indicating that they are very satisfied with their workload, working conditions, administrative support, and opportunities for professional growth. This suggests that they feel fulfilled in their teaching roles, which may encourage them to remain in their current institution. The results also reveal a very high level of emotional attachment, showing strong feelings of belonging, connection, and commitment to students, colleagues, and the school culture. In addition, teachers demonstrate a very high level of commitment and loyalty, reflecting dedication to their work and alignment with school goals, although some concerns about long-term retention remain. Furthermore, there is no significant difference in affective factors when grouped according to length of service, while a significant difference is observed when grouped according to position, indicating that roles and responsibilities influence teachers' perceptions and experiences in the school.

Recommendations

The findings suggest that school administrators should strengthen communication, support systems, and participatory decision-making to further enhance teachers' job satisfaction, emotional attachment, and commitment, which may improve retention. Teachers are encouraged to maintain positive relationships with colleagues, students, and school leaders, actively engage in professional development, and openly communicate concerns to improve their work experience. Students should continue showing respect, cooperation, and appreciation toward teachers to promote a positive school environment. Private school institutions are encouraged to sustain and further improve working conditions, professional growth opportunities, and institutional support to maintain high levels of teacher retention. Future researchers are advised to explore additional factors such as salary, workload, leadership style, and school culture, and to conduct similar studies in other schools to strengthen and validate the findings of this research.

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